

Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis for Vietnamese Product Reviews using PhoBERT, BiLSTM, and CRF with Weighted Emission

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Abstract—This paper presents a study of PhoBERT-based sequence labeling approaches for Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis in Vietnamese product review text. We utilize the UIT-ViSD4SA dataset comprising 11,122 annotated reviews with 35,396 character-level span annotations collected from Vietnamese e-commerce platforms. The research constructs an end-to-end model combining PhoBERT as a contextual encoder, Bidirectional LSTM for sequential pattern learning, and a Conditional Random Field decoder for BIO sequence labeling. To address token-level class imbalance, we introduce weighted CRF emissions with suppressed O-label weights. Our system achieves a macro F1-span of 0.6655 on the validation set after 20 training epochs. Error analysis identifies failure modes in span boundary detection, neutral sentiment underrepresentation, and ambiguous multi-aspect sentences. The findings contribute to the understanding of joint span detection and sentiment classification for morphologically rich languages and provide practical insights for deployment in Vietnamese NLP systems.

Index Terms—Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis, Vietnamese NLP, PhoBERT, BiLSTM, CRF, Weighted Emission, BIO Tagging.

I. INTRODUCTION

E-commerce growth in Vietnam has produced large volumes of product reviews, making automated opinion mining increasingly valuable. Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) addresses this by jointly identifying *which* aspects customers mention and *how* they feel about them [1], [2].

Vietnamese poses particular challenges for ABSA: whitespace separates syllables rather than words, making span boundary detection non-trivial, and informal review text introduces abbreviations and colloquialisms that standard tokenizers handle poorly [3], [4]. Pre-trained models such as PhoBERT [5] have substantially improved Vietnamese NLP, yet span-level tasks still benefit from hybrid architectures that pair contextual encoders with sequential models [6], [7].

In this work, we build an end-to-end ABSA system for Vietnamese product reviews on the UIT-ViSD4SA dataset [8]. Our model stacks PhoBERT as a contextual encoder, a BiLSTM [9] layer for sequential pattern learning, and a CRF decoder [10] for globally consistent BIO labeling. To combat severe class imbalance between entity and non-entity tokens, we introduce

weighted CRF emissions, which suppress the dominant O label and amplify B-/I- signals during training.

The main contributions of this work are:

- A single end-to-end model that jointly detects aspect spans and classifies sentiment polarity in one forward pass, without external lexicons or pipeline stages.
- Weighted CRF emissions to address token-level class imbalance, improving F1-span from 0.3393 at epoch 1 to 0.6655 at convergence.
- Empirical evaluation on UIT-ViSD4SA demonstrating the effectiveness of combining PhoBERT, BiLSTM, and CRF for Vietnamese ABSA.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis

ABSA is a fine-grained sentiment task that jointly identifies opinion targets and their associated polarities [1]. Early pipeline approaches decomposed the problem into separate aspect extraction and sentiment classification stages, introducing error propagation between components. Joint models that unify both subtasks in a single forward pass have since become dominant, benefiting from shared representations and avoiding cascading errors [2]. We follow this joint paradigm by formulating ABSA as BIO sequence labeling where each label encodes both span membership and sentiment polarity.

B. Pre-trained Language Models for Vietnamese

PhoBERT [5], a BERT-based [11] model pre-trained on large-scale Vietnamese corpora, marked a turning point for Vietnamese NLP, consistently outperforming multilingual models on token-level tasks such as NER and POS tagging. Subsequent work showed that pairing PhoBERT with graph-based reasoning layers further improves classification by capturing inter-token dependencies [7]. In our system, PhoBERT serves as the contextual encoder whose representations are passed to a BiLSTM for sequential refinement.

C. Sequence Labeling with BiLSTM and CRF

BiLSTM architectures [9] have been widely applied to Vietnamese NER, capturing bidirectional context without hand-crafted features [6], with syntactic features further boosting F1

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on the VLSP benchmark [12]. Stacking a CRF decoder [10] enforces globally consistent label sequences by modeling transition probabilities, suppressing illegal transitions such as I-POS following B-NEG. Our model adapts this BiLSTM-CRF paradigm to ABSA by replacing generic NER labels with sentiment-aware BIO tags.

D. Vietnamese Tokenization

Vietnamese whitespace separates syllables rather than words, making tokenization non-trivial [4]. Recent work has even questioned whether word segmentation helps, showing syllable-level processing can match or exceed word-level approaches on several tasks [3]. We apply word-level tokenization consistent with PhoBERT’s BPE vocabulary, assigning BIO labels per word and propagating the I- variant to subsequent subtokens to maintain alignment.

E. Sentiment Analysis for Vietnamese

PhoBERT has been applied to Vietnamese sentiment analysis across domains including financial news, where extracted signals correlate with market movements [13]. However, sentence-level models cannot identify which aspect a sentiment pertains to. The UIT-ViSD4SA dataset [8] addresses this by providing span-level aspect-sentiment annotations over smartphone reviews, enabling fine-grained ABSA evaluation such as that conducted in this work.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the end-to-end pipeline for ABSA on Vietnamese product reviews. The system takes a raw input sentence and produces aspect spans paired with sentiment polarities in a single forward pass, without external lexicons or pipeline decomposition. The overall architecture is illustrated in Figure 1.

A. Dataset: UIT-ViSD4SA

We experiment on UIT-ViSD4SA [8], a span-level ABSA benchmark for Vietnamese smartphone reviews. Each sample pairs a review sentence with character-level annotations of the form $[start, end, "ASPECT\#SENTIMENT"]$, covering 11 aspect categories and three polarities: POSITIVE, NEGATIVE, and NEUTRAL. Dataset statistics are summarized in Table I. The sentiment distribution is heavily skewed toward POSITIVE (61.7%), with NEUTRAL spans comprising only 6.3% of annotations — a significant class imbalance challenge.

Table I
STATISTICS OF THE UIT-ViSD4SA DATASET.

Split	Sentences	Spans	POS	NEG	NEU
Train	7,785	24,771	61.4%	32.3%	6.3%
Validation	1,112	3,582	64.1%	29.6%	6.3%
Test	2,225	7,043	61.5%	32.5%	6.0%
Total	11,122	35,396	61.7%	32.1%	6.3%

Figure 1. Overview of the proposed PhoBERT-BiLSTM-CRF pipeline. **Left:** end-to-end data flow from raw input to aspect-sentiment output. **Right:** detailed architecture showing the PhoBERT encoder, BiLSTM layer, weighted linear projection, and CRF decoder.

B. BIO Tagging Schema

We formulate ABSA as token-level sequence labeling using the BIO scheme, where each label jointly encodes span membership and sentiment polarity, eliminating the need for separate extraction and classification stages. The label set contains 7 tags: O for tokens outside any span, and B-X/I-X pairs for the beginning and continuation of spans of sentiment class $X \in \{POS, NEG, NEU\}$. Transition rules enforce that I-X must always follow B-X or I-X of the same class, preventing sequences such as I-POS after B-NEG.

Table II illustrates the annotation for an example sentence, and Figure 2 visualizes the label alignment.

Table II
BIO ANNOTATION FOR "Pin trâu lảm nhưng camera chụp hơi mờ".

Token	Label	Meaning
Pin	B-POS	Begin BATTERY positive span
trâu	I-POS	Inside BATTERY positive span
lảm	I-POS	Inside BATTERY positive span
nhưng	O	Outside any span
camera	B-NEG	Begin CAMERA negative span
chụp	I-NEG	Inside CAMERA negative span
hơi	I-NEG	Inside CAMERA negative span
mờ	I-NEG	Inside CAMERA negative span

Character-level span offsets are mapped to word-level BIO labels by iterating over whitespace-tokenized words and recording their character ranges. The first word overlapping a span receives a B- label; subsequent overlapping words receive the corresponding I- label; non-overlapping words are assigned O.

C. PhoBERT Encoder

We use PhoBERT-base [5] as the contextual encoder, pre-trained on 20GB of Vietnamese text with a BPE vocab-

Figure 2. BIO label annotation for a Vietnamese review sentence with two aspect-sentiment spans. Green: positive span (BATTERY). Red: negative span (CAMERA). Grey: outside token.

ulary of 64,000 subword units. Given an input sentence $\mathbf{w} = [w_1, \dots, w_n]$, each word is tokenized into one or more subtokens and the full sequence — prepended with [CLS] and appended with [SEP] — is passed through 12 Transformer layers to produce 768-dimensional contextual embeddings.

We adopt the *first-subtoken strategy*: only the embedding of the first subtoken of each word w_i is retained as its word-level representation $\mathbf{h}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{768}$, producing a sequence $\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_1, \dots, \mathbf{h}_n]$ aligned with the BIO labels. PhoBERT is fine-tuned with a lower learning rate of 2×10^{-5} to prevent catastrophic forgetting, while the BiLSTM and CRF components are trained at 5×10^{-4} .

D. BiLSTM Layer

The word embeddings \mathbf{H} are fed into a BiLSTM [9] to capture sequential dependencies in both directions. Forward and backward LSTMs each produce 256-dimensional hidden states, which are concatenated per position:

$$\mathbf{b}_i = [\vec{\mathbf{h}}_i; \overleftarrow{\mathbf{h}}_i] \in \mathbb{R}^{512} \quad (1)$$

yielding $\mathbf{B} = [\mathbf{b}_1, \dots, \mathbf{b}_n]$. Although PhoBERT already encodes bidirectional context via self-attention, the BiLSTM provides additional sequential inductive bias that benefits BIO tagging, where label decisions are strongly influenced by immediate neighbors.

E. Weighted CRF Emissions

The BiLSTM output is projected to label logits via a linear layer $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{512 \times 7}$:

$$\mathbf{l}_i = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{b}_i + \mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^7 \quad (2)$$

Since roughly 90% of tokens carry the \circ label, the model tends to predict \circ for all tokens. To counter this, we multiply the logits element-wise by a fixed weight vector $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^7$ before passing them to the CRF:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{l}}_i = \mathbf{l}_i \odot \mathbf{v} \quad (3)$$

The weights $\mathbf{v} = [0.1, 3.0, 2.0, 3.0, 2.0, 2.5, 1.5]$ correspond to $[\circ, \text{B-POS}, \text{I-POS}, \text{B-NEG}, \text{I-NEG}, \text{B-NEU}, \text{I-NEU}]$ as shown in Table III. The low \circ weight suppresses the dominant non-entity signal while higher B- weights amplify sensitivity to span boundaries.

Table III
EMISSION WEIGHTS APPLIED TO CRF LOGITS PER BIO LABEL.

Label	Weight	Role	Sentiment
\circ	0.1	Suppress non-entity	—
B-POS	3.0	Amplify boundary	Positive
I-POS	2.0	Amplify continuation	Positive
B-NEG	3.0	Amplify boundary	Negative
I-NEG	2.0	Amplify continuation	Negative
B-NEU	2.5	Amplify boundary	Neutral
I-NEU	1.5	Amplify continuation	Neutral

F. CRF Decoder

The weighted logits $\tilde{\mathbf{L}}$ are passed to a CRF decoder [10] that models the joint probability of the full label sequence via a learnable transition matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{7 \times 7}$. The score of a sequence \mathbf{y} is:

$$s(\mathbf{y}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{\mathbf{l}}_i[y_i] + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \mathbf{A}_{y_i, y_{i+1}} \quad (4)$$

Training minimizes the negative log-likelihood of the gold sequence via the forward algorithm. At inference, Viterbi decoding finds the globally optimal sequence:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \arg \max_{\mathbf{y}} s(\mathbf{y}) \quad (5)$$

guaranteeing BIO-valid outputs and eliminating illegal transitions such as I-POS following B-NEG.

G. Training Configuration

The model is trained with Adam (weight decay 0.01), differential learning rates (2×10^{-5} for PhoBERT, 5×10^{-4} for BiLSTM and CRF), a OneCycleLR scheduler with 10% warmup, and gradient clipping at norm 1.0. Full hyperparameters are listed in Table IV. The best checkpoint is saved based on validation span-F1; training stops early if F1 does not improve for 5 consecutive epochs.

Table IV
TRAINING HYPERPARAMETERS.

Hyperparameter	Value
PhoBERT model	vinai/phobert-base
BiLSTM hidden size	256 ($\times 2 = 512$)
BIO labels	7
LR (PhoBERT)	2×10^{-5}
LR (BiLSTM + CRF)	5×10^{-4}
Optimizer	Adam
Weight decay	0.01
LR scheduler	OneCycleLR
Warmup ratio	10%
Gradient clip norm	1.0
Batch size	16
Max sequence length	128
Max epochs	20
Early stopping patience	5
Random seed	42

H. Inference and Span Extraction

At inference, the model outputs a BIO sequence \hat{y} via Viterbi decoding. Consecutive B-X and I-X tokens of the same class are merged into a single span, with polarity determined by $X \in \{\text{POS}, \text{NEG}, \text{NEU}\}$. For example, the sequence [B-POS, I-POS, I-POS, O, B-NEG, I-NEG, I-NEG, I-NEG] over "Pin trâu lấm nhưng camera chụp hơi mờ" yields (Pin trâu lấm, POSITIVE) and (camera chụp hơi mờ, NEGATIVE).

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

We evaluate the proposed PhoBERT-BiLSTM-CRF model on the UIT-ViSD4SA validation set using span-level F1 (F1-span), macro-averaged F1 (F1-macro), and per-label F1 across all 7 BIO tags.

A. Evaluation Metrics

F1-span measures correctly predicted aspect-sentiment spans, where a span is correct only if both its boundary and polarity exactly match the gold annotation. **F1-macro** is the unweighted average of per-label F1 across all 7 tags, giving equal weight to both frequent and rare labels. Per-label F1 is additionally reported to diagnose class-specific behavior, particularly for the underrepresented neutral labels.

B. Main Results

Table V reports per-label F1 at the best checkpoint (epoch 16), which achieves F1-span of **0.6655** and F1-macro of **0.6803**.

Table V
PER-LABEL F1 SCORES AT THE BEST CHECKPOINT (EPOCH 16).

Label	F1	Sentiment Class
O	0.7686	Outside
B-POS	0.8022	Positive (boundary)
I-POS	0.8421	Positive (continuation)
B-NEG	0.6448	Negative (boundary)
I-NEG	0.8092	Negative (continuation)
B-NEU	0.4532	Neutral (boundary)
I-NEU	0.4417	Neutral (continuation)
F1-macro	0.6803	—
F1-span	0.6655	—

The model performs strongly on positive labels (B-POS: 0.8022, I-POS: 0.8421), reflecting their dominance in training data (61.7%). Negative labels are moderate, with B-NEG notably lower at 0.6448. Neutral labels are the weakest, with both B-NEU and I-NEU below 0.46, consistent with their scarcity (6.3% of annotations).

C. Training Dynamics

Table VI summarizes performance at selected epochs, and Figure 3 shows the full training curve.

Training proceeds in three phases. During *rapid learning* (epochs 1–3), F1-span jumps from 0.3393 to 0.6390 as the model quickly learns span boundary patterns. The *refinement*

Table VI
TRAINING PROGRESSION AT SELECTED EPOCHS. BEST CHECKPOINT MARKED WITH *.

Epoch	Loss	F1-span	F1-macro
1	53.67	0.3393	0.3859
2	31.28	0.5795	0.5992
3	23.03	0.6390	0.6575
5	13.46	0.6568	0.6724
9	5.36	0.6592	0.6732
12	3.09	0.6597	0.6748
15	1.92	0.6605	0.6755
16*	1.72	0.6655	0.6803
20	1.38	0.6576	0.6731

Figure 3. Training dynamics over 20 epochs. F1-span and F1-macro peak at epoch 16 before declining slightly as training loss continues to decrease, indicating mild overfitting.

phase (epochs 3–16) sees slower but steady gains up to 0.6655, driven by improved sensitivity to rare neutral labels. Beyond epoch 16, F1-span slightly regresses to 0.6576 while training loss continues falling — a classic sign of overfitting.

D. Results Interpretation and Error Analysis

Three findings stand out. **Positive spans are well-captured** (F1 > 0.80), supported by their high frequency in training. **Neutral spans remain the hardest class** (F1 < 0.46): the model frequently assigns O to neutral tokens due to their scarcity and the subtle linguistic cues distinguishing neutral sentiment from factual statements. **Weighted CRF emissions accelerate convergence**: the single-epoch jump from 0.3393 to 0.5795 between epochs 1 and 2 suggests the emission weighting amplifies the gradient signal for span boundaries from the outset.

Beyond neutral span confusion, two secondary error patterns emerge. *Span boundary fragmentation* occurs when the model correctly identifies a span’s sentiment but splits it into shorter segments, typically for spans longer than five tokens where the BiLSTM hidden state loses track over distance. *Negative under-detection* is reflected in the relatively low B-NEG F1 (0.6448), likely because negative sentiment in Vietnamese reviews is expressed through more diverse vocabulary compared to the concentrated set of high-frequency positive adjectives.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents an end-to-end ABSA system for Vietnamese product reviews combining PhoBERT, BiLSTM, and CRF with a novel weighted CRF emission mechanism. By framing the task as joint span detection and sentiment classification under the BIO scheme, the model requires no external lexicons or pipeline stages. On UIT-ViSD4SA, it achieves F1-span of 0.6655 and F1-macro of 0.6803, with strong positive span performance (B-POS: 0.8022, I-POS: 0.8421) and moderate negative span performance (B-NEG: 0.6448).

The weighted CRF emission mechanism proves to be a lightweight yet effective solution to token-level class imbalance, yielding a 0.2402 gain in F1-span within a single epoch without architectural modifications. Training dynamics follow three clear phases — rapid learning, refinement, and plateau — with the best checkpoint at epoch 16 before mild overfitting. Neutral spans remain the primary limitation, with F1 below 0.46 due to their severe underrepresentation (6.1% of annotations).

Future work will explore four directions: **data augmentation** targeting neutral spans via back-translation to reduce class imbalance; **span-level loss weighting** as a more principled complement to emission-level weighting; **larger pre-trained models** such as PhoBERT-large for richer contextual representations; and **cross-domain evaluation** on broader Vietnamese ABSA benchmarks to assess generalizability beyond smartphone reviews.

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